

The air-broadening coefficients of HO₂

Different measurements have more recently been made of the air-broadening coefficients of HO₂ from infrared and submillimeter-wave spectra [1-6]. The current air-broadening coefficient of the hydroperoxyl radical in the HITRAN database is a constant, $\gamma_{\text{air}}=0.107\pm 0.009\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (based on the measurement in Ref.[2]) for all the lines. All the available experimental results have been collected in Table 1. A decrease of the air-broadening coefficients with increasing ($N''+0.2K_a''$) quantum number can be seen in Fig.1. It does not seem that there is a strong vibrational dependence, which is not typical for non-linear molecules. In Ref. [3], the measurements were averaged for every N'' value and linear dependence was suggested as a function of N'' .

Fig.1 the air-broadening coefficients plotted as a function of the lower state rotational quantum number ($N''+0.2K_a''$)

Here the index ($N''+0.2K_a''$) instead of N'' was chosen as it better demonstrates the K_a -dependence. A linear fit was carried out, and the corresponding coefficients are given in Table 2.

The following approach is suggested. We will use experimental values for all the transitions with corresponding rotational quantum numbers (in all the bands). For everything else we will use the linear extrapolation (from Table 2) up to ($N''+0.2K_a''$) < 17. For ($N''+0.2K_a''$) > 17, the value corresponding to the experimental value with the largest ($N''+0.2K_a''$) will be used.

Table 1

HO₂ (N₂⁻, O₂⁻) air-broadening coefficients (in cm⁻¹/atm)

Ref	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	Transitions (N K _g K _c)	Hyperfine J'-J''	γ _{N2}	γ _{O2}	γ _{air}
[1]	83.3178	13 _{2,12} -12 _{1,11}	13.5-12.5	0.160(15)	0.068(5)	0.142(13)
[2]	1411.18	9 _{1,9} -8 _{1,8}	8.5-7.5			0.107(9)
		9 _{1,9} -8 _{1,8}	9.5-8.5			0.107(9)
[3]	6631.0019	6 _{0,6} -6 _{1,5}				0.0967(112)
	6631.0884	7 _{0,7} -7 _{1,6}				0.0901(113)
	6631.1887	5 _{0,5} -5 _{1,4}				0.0948(143)
	6631.3129	4 _{0,4} -4 _{1,3}				0.1251(81)
	6631.3701	3 _{0,3} -3 _{1,2}				0.1244(104)
	6631.4543	8 _{0,8} -9 _{0,9}				0.1394(188)
	6631.4772	*				0.0964(248)
	6631.6137	5 _{0,5} -5 _{1,4}				0.1421(94)
	6631.8267	4 _{0,4} -4 _{1,3}				0.1178(146)
	6666.5915	8 _{1,8} -7 _{1,7}				0.1185(30)
	6666.6411	8 _{1,8} -7 _{1,7}				0.1277(80)
	6666.8618	10 _{2,9} -9 _{2,8}				0.1548(56)
	6666.9080	10 _{2,9} -9 _{2,8}				0.1204(158)
	6667.0197	*				0.1287(190)
	6667.0640	10 _{2,8} -9 _{2,7}				0.1308(266)
	6667.2771	8 _{1,7} -7 _{1,6}				0.1170(115)
	6667.3226	8 _{1,7} -7 _{1,6}				0.1207(132)
	6669.0059	11 _{2,9} -10 _{2,8}				0.0882(66)
	6669.0766	11 _{2,10} -10 _{2,9}				0.1128(69)
	6669.1142	4 _{1,3} -4 _{0,4}				0.1399(111)
	6669.1383	11 _{2,9} -10 _{2,8}				0.0780(33)
	6669.2982	5 _{1,4} -5 _{0,5}				0.1307(106)
	6669.4163	9 _{1,8} -8 _{1,7}				0.1225(116)
	6669.4464	9 _{1,8} -8 _{1,7}				0.0993(94)
	6669.4916	6 _{1,5} -6 _{0,6}				0.1169(132)
	6669.5197	3 _{1,2} -3 _{0,3}				0.1447(184)
	6669.6789	5 _{1,4} -5 _{0,5}				0.0855(39)
	6669.7049	7 _{1,6} -7 _{0,7}				0.0823(22)
	6669.9261	8 _{1,7} -8 _{0,8}				0.1210(75)
	6670.0064	7 _{1,6} -7 _{0,7}				0.1174(68)
	6670.0951	*				0.0938(98)
	6670.1514	9 _{1,8} -9 _{0,9}				0.1030(110)
	6670.2049	8 _{1,7} -8 _{0,8}				0.0959(77)
	6670.2696	*				0.1404(44)
[4]	1064.909	13 _{0,13} -14 _{0,14}	12.5-13.5	0.118(11)		
	1064.913	13 _{0,13} -14 _{0,14}	13.5-14.5	0.099(9)		
	1065.203	13 _{1,13} -14 _{1,14}	13.5-14.5	0.095(5)		

	1065.221	13 _{1,13} -14 _{1,14}	12.5–13.5	0.090(5)		
[5]	8.865	4 _{1,3} -3 _{1,2}	4.5 -3.5	0.103(2)		
	20.869	10 _{1,9} -10 _{0,10}	10.5-10.5	0.104(1)	0.065(1)	0.0955(17)
	21.403	10 _{1,10} -9 _{1,9}	9.5 -8.5	0.103(1)	0.064(1)	0.0948(15)
	21.671	10 _{2,9} -9 _{2,8}	9.5 -8.5	0.088(2)	0.066(3)	0.0836(25)
[6]	1060.172	15 _{1,15} -16 _{1,16}	15.5–16.5	0.120(4)	0.075(4)	0.111(4)
	1060.186	15 _{1,15} -16 _{1,16}	14.5–15.5	0.091(7)	0.062(2)	0.085(6)
	1062.089	14 _{3,11} -15 _{3,12}	13.5–14.5	0.092(7)	0.066(7)	0.087(7)
	1062.090	14 _{3,12} -15 _{3,13}	13.5–14.5	0.092(7)	0.066(7)	0.087(7)
	1062.102	14 _{2,12} -15 _{2,13}	14.5–15.5	0.124(13)	0.077(5)	0.114(11)
	1062.165	14 _{2,12} -15 _{2,13}	13.5–14.5	0.086(5)	0.052(3)	0.079(4)
	1062.171	14 _{2,13} -15 _{2,14}	14.5–15.5	0.079(10)	0.057(1)	0.074(8)
	1062.236	14 _{2,13} -15 _{2,14}	13.5–14.5	0.116(26)	0.077(4)	0.108(21)
	1062.700	14 _{1,14} -15 _{1,15}	14.5–15.5	0.093(21)	0.072(4)	0.088(18)
	1062.716	14 _{1,14} -15 _{1,15}	13.5–14.5	0.107(5)	0.066(5)	0.099(5)
	1064.630	13 _{3,10} -14 _{3,11}	12.5–13.5	0.103(9)	0.071(3)	0.096(8)
	1064.631	13 _{3,11} -14 _{3,12}	12.5–13.5	0.103(9)	0.071(3)	0.096(8)
	1064.639	13 _{2,11} -14 _{2,12}	13.5–14.5	0.113(5)	0.071(6)	0.104(5)
	1064.696	13 _{2,12} -14 _{2,13}	13.5–14.5	0.099(10)	0.073(4)	0.094(9)
	1064.710	13 _{2,11} -14 _{2,12}	12.5–13.5	0.111(12)	0.080(18)	0.104(13)
	1064.768	13 _{2,12} -14 _{2,13}	12.5–13.5	0.101(15)	0.074(4)	0.095(13)
	1064.909	13 _{0,13} -14 _{0,14}	12.5–13.5	0.083(15)	0.063(7)	0.079(13)
	1064.913	13 _{0,13} -14 _{0,14}	13.5–14.5	0.097(14)	0.064(5)	0.090(12)
	1065.203	13 _{1,13} -14 _{1,14}	13.5–14.5	0.118(5)	0.068(6)	0.107(5)
	1065.221	13 _{1,13} -14 _{1,14}	12.5–13.5	0.105(26)	0.070(2)	0.098(21)

Note: All experiments have been made at room temperature, so the temperature dependence of γ_{air} has been neglected;
 *Lines without assignment.

Table2

Linear fit: Y= a+b*X	value	Standard Error
Intercept	0.1367	0.005
Slope	-0.0027	5E-4

References

- [1] Chance K, Denatale P, Bellini M, Inguscio M, Dilonardo G, Fusina L. Pressure Broadening of the 2.4978-THz Rotational Lines of HO₂ by N₂ and O₂. J Mol Spectrosc 1994;163:67–70. doi:10.1006/jmsp.1994.1007.
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- [3] Ibrahim N, Thiebaud J, Orphal J, Fittschen C. Air-broadening coefficients of the HO₂ radical in the 2ν₁ band measured using cw-CRDS. *J Mol Spectrosc* 2007;242:64–9. doi:10.1016/j.jms.2007.02.007.
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- [5] A.Mizoguchi, T.Yagi, K.Kondo, T.O.Sato, H.Kanamori. Submillimeter-wave measurements of N₂ and O₂ pressure broadening for HO₂ radical generated by Hg-photosensitized reaction. *J Quant Spectrosc Radiat Transf* 2012;113:279–85. doi:10.1016/j.jqsrt.2011.11.009.
- [6] Minamida M, Tonokura K. Air broadening coefficients for the ν₃ band of hydroperoxyl radicals. *J Quant Spectrosc Radiat Transf* 2014;148:65–9. doi:10.1016/j.jqsrt.2014.06.020.

Details of the γ_{air} in HITRAN

Values for HO₂ γ_{air}

- ✓ We use the experimental results for the measured transitions in the specific bands.

Wavenumber(cm ⁻¹)	γ_{air}	Error Code	Ref. Code
1411.182082	0.107	5	1
1411.182506	0.107	5	1
20.869791	0.0955	6	4
21.402922	0.0948	7	4
21.671709	0.0836	6	4
1060.171729	0.111	6	5
1060.185559	0.085	5	5
1062.089333	0.087	5	5
1062.090479	0.087	5	5
1062.101994	0.114	4	5
1062.164996	0.079	5	5

1062.171305	0.074	4	5
1062.235623	0.108	4	5
1062.700079	0.088	3	5
1062.715515	0.099	5	5
1064.630080	0.096	5	5
1064.630900	0.096	5	5
1064.638797	0.104	5	5
1064.695843	0.094	4	5
1064.709590	0.104	4	5
1064.767798	0.095	4	5
1064.709590	0.079	4	5
1064.767798	0.090	4	5
1065.203385	0.107	5	5
1065.220768	0.098	3	5

- ✓ We also use weighted average experimental values for all the transitions with corresponding rotational quantum numbers (in all the bands).

Transitions ($N' K_a' K_c' - N'' K_a'' K_c''$)	γ_{air_exp}	$\gamma_{air_weighted}$ mean	Error Code	Ref. Code
3 0 3 - 3 1 2	0.1244(104)	0.1244	5	3
3 1 2 - 3 0 3	0.1447(184)	0.1447	4	3
4 0 4 - 4 1 3	0.1251(81)	0.1204	5	3
	0.1178(146)			
4 1 3 - 4 0 4	0.1399(111)	0.1399	5	3
5 0 5 - 5 1 4	0.1421(94)	0.1136	4	3
	0.0948(143)			
5 1 4 - 5 0 5	0.1307(106)	0.1185	5	3
	0.0855(39)			
6 0 6 - 6 1 5	0.0967(112)	0.0967	4	3
6 1 5 - 6 0 6	0.1169(132)	0.1169	4	3
7 0 7 - 7 1 6	0.0901(113)	0.0901	4	3
7 1 6 - 7 0 7	0.0823(22)	0.1088	6	3
	0.1174(68)			
8 0 8 - 9 0 9	0.1394(188)	0.1394	4	3
8 1 7 - 7 1 6	0.1170(115)	0.1190	4	3
	0.1207(132)			
8 1 7 - 8 0 8	0.1210(75)	0.1083	5	3
	0.0959(77)			
8 1 8 - 7 1 7	0.1185(30)	0.1252	6	3
	0.1277(80)			
9 1 8 - 8 1 7	0.1225(116)	0.1121	5	3
	0.0993(94)			
9 1 8 - 9 0 9	0.1030(110)	0.1030	4	3

9 1 9 - 8 1 8	0.107(9)	0.1070	5	1
10 1 9 - 10 0 10	0.0955(17)	0.0955	6	4
10 1 10 - 9 1 9	0.0948(15)	0.0948	7	4
10 2 8 - 9 2 7	0.1308(266)	0.1308	3	3
10 2 9 - 9 2 8	0.0836(25)	0.0836	6	4
	0.1548(56)			3
	0.1204(158)			3
11 2 9 - 10 2 8	0.0882(66)	0.0848	5	3
	0.0780(33)			
11 2 10 - 10 2 9	0.1128(69)	0.1128	5	3
13 0 13 - 14 0 14	0.079(13)	0.0843	4	5
	0.090(12)			
13 1 13 - 14 1 14	0.107(5)	0.0997	4	5
	0.098(21)			
13 2 11 - 14 2 12	0.104(5)	0.1040	5	5
	0.104(13)			
13 2 12 - 14 2 13	0.094(9)	0.0946	4	5
	0.095(13)			
13 3 10 - 14 3 11	0.096(8)	0.0960	5	5
13 3 11 - 14 3 12	0.096(8)	0.0960	5	5
14 1 14 - 15 1 15	0.088(18)	0.0904	4	5
	0.099(5)			
14 2 12 - 15 2 13	0.114(11)	0.1047	5	5
	0.079(4)			
14 2 13 - 15 2 14	0.074(8)	0.0986	4	5
	0.108(21)			
14 3 11 - 15 3 12	0.087(7)	0.0870	5	5
14 3 12 - 15 3 13	0.087(7)	0.0870	5	5
15 1 15 - 16 1 16	0.111(4)	0.0954	5	5
	0.085(6)			

*For transition [10 2 9 - 9 2 8], we have three measurements in two different bands. And we choose the best experimental result $\gamma_{\text{air}} = 0.0836$ instead of the average value.

- ✓ For the rest of these transitions, we use the linear extrapolation (from Table2) up to $(N''+0.2Ka'') < 17$. And for $(N''+0.2Ka'') > 17$, $\gamma_{\text{air}}(16.2) = 0.0930$ will be used.
The error code calculated to be 4, and the ref. number will be 6 represent this report.

Ref table for HO₂ γ_{air}

For old HO₂ γ_{air} ref:

Half-widths (air)

1. D.D. Nelson and M.S. Zahniser “Air broadening measurements for the v_2 vibrational band of the hydroperoxyl radical,” *J.Mol.Spectrosc.* **166**, 273-279 (1994).
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Add new references(3-6):

- [3] Ibrahim N, Thiebaud J, Orphal J, Fittschen C. Air-broadening coefficients of the HO₂ radical in the 2v₁ band measured using cw-CRDS. *J Mol Spectrosc* 2007;242:64–9. doi:10.1016/j.jms.2007.02.007.
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- [5] Minamida M, Tonokura K. Air broadening coefficients for the v₃ band of hydroperoxyl radicals. *J Quant Spectrosc Radiat Transf* 2014;148:65–9. doi:10.1016/j.jqsrt.2014.06.020.
- [6] This report for linear fit of HO₂ γ_{air}